

WHO WAS MUKIMI?

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7614126>

Abstract: In this paper works written by the prominent poet and literary critic Mukimi are researched. Mukimi's literary activity is vast and his contribution to the development of Uzbek literature is of great value. These issues are analyzed in the paper.

Key words: Mukimi, travelogues, literary activity, literature, poet, ghazal, literary work, to criticize, stanza.

In the years of independence, as in all spheres of the life of our society, a wide path has been opened for research related to the illumination of our national identity, re-studying the unknown pages of the history of our statehood, the history of our national literature, unreasonably forgotten artists and the rich scientific knowledge of our thinking in socio-political and spiritual directions.

It should be noted that classic literary works occupy an important place in the literary and historical heritage of the Uzbek people. A true study of such works, our heritage, and their scientific analysis is one of the urgent tasks of our day.

One of the centers of Uzbek national culture of the 19th-20th centuries was undoubtedly the city of Kokand. Here, in the first half of the 18th-19th centuries, great poets and thinkers, whose names are world-famous in the world of science and enlightenment, grew up here. In particular, in the 19th century, thanks to the efforts of Khan of Kokand Umar Khan (1810-1822) and his companion poet Nadira, a literary atmosphere of knowledge and enlightenment appeared in the city of Kokand. The creative people who have cultivated this literary environment have been active participants of the literary movement in different periods of our development. Their works have become the immortal spiritual property of our people. In 20th century literary studies, the history of classical literature, in particular, its creators, is given a one-sided assessment. For various reasons, some literary works have not been studied. Based on this, if we look at the history of Uzbek literature, the historiography of the Soviet era tried to paint the history of the Uzbek people in the fields of science and culture in the 13th-19th centuries as much as possible. In that period, poets and writers were described as careerists and flatterers gathered around the palace. While the work of the representatives of the Kokand literary environment was studied in the literary studies of the Soviet period, their activities were treated in a one-sided manner. In particular, Adoni was introduced as a representative of feudal-

clerical literature. About him and others like him: «Malik ush-shuaro» («King of poets») of Umar Khan's court, Sultankhoja Tora Ado and his associates had the same class interests. «The khans were the leaders of such groups, that is, the ruling feudal aristocracy, the defenders of the interests of this class, or rather, the executors of the demands of that class».(2)

The work covers a century-long history of studies about Mukimi, using comparative and historical-typological methods.

One of such creators is Muhammad Aminkhoja Mukimi, who has a well-deserved place in the history of Uzbek literature. The poet was born in 1850 in Bekvachcha neighborhood (now Mukimi street) of Kokand city. His father, Mirzakhoja Mirfazil, was a baker, and his mother, Bibioysha, was the daughter of Sayidolim Nadirshaikh. The role of his mother in having a poetic nature is incomparable. Because his mother has an excellent education, she knows oral creativity very well. Thanks to this woman, Mukimi's poetic talent develops. He wrote his first poem at the age of ten. There were five children in the permanent family, and there was a third child. Muhammad Aminkhoja studied at the school of teacher Abdusalil in his neighborhood. He was also interested in calligraphy and learned husnikhat from the famous Kokan calligrapher Muhammad Yusuf. From the age of 15-16, the poet began to write poems under the pseudonym «Mukimi» («permanence»3).

Then, according to some reports, he studied at Hokimoyim madrasa in Kokand and Bukhara madrasas and mastered Arabic and Persian languages. After graduating from Madrasa in Kokand, he went to Bukhara to continue his education. He was engaged in education there for several years and was known as a mature and leading poet of his time. Mukimi returned to Kokan after completing his studies in 1876. He was cautiously welcomed and not accepted by the Kokan nobles. As the poet himself wrote, «It was the unpleasant Kokan nobility that allowed me to review my views and develop new moral and literary views in myself. My frustration helped me a lot». In studying the life and work of a writer in literature classes, the information about his author has a special place. Where does this information come from? They can be taken from the biographies written down by the writers themselves, from contemporaries, peers, teachers or students, acquaintances and admirers of the writer, or from written sources.

The list of used literature:

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